

Nature Of Teaching Evaluation Practices In Universities Of Pakistan From The Perspective Of Their Orientation Towards Quality Assurance And Enhancement

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Abstract

The last decades have observed increasing demands from the public and the governments for evaluating the performance of universities. This phenomenon has consequently led to the measures for evaluating the performance of faculty members in universities in areas of teaching, research, scholarship, creative work, and services offered to the community. Of these, evaluation of teaching is the key but the complex phenomenon. The literature reveals that an effective system for the evaluation of teaching in universities should address the needs of accountability and improvement. In this context, the aim of this research is thus to investigate the nature of teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation and focus either towards quality assurance (accountability), quality enhancement (improvement), or the both. The research used triangulation mixed-method research design and both qualitative and quantitative data were collected and analyzed simultaneously. In phase I, 71 policy and practice documents related to evaluation of teaching were collected from the HEC and 130 universities of Pakistan. In phase II, the survey technique was used to identify the nature of current teacher evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation towards improvement and accountability. A self-developed questionnaire with 26 statements, and orientation of evaluation practices towards improvement and accountability was administered to 617 faculty members. For the analysis of policy documents, thematic analysis was used while quantitative data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, mean, SD, Chi-Square test and t-test. The findings of policy documents revealed that teaching evaluation practices are not satisfying purposes of accountability and improvement in universities of Pakistan. Likewise, the focus of evaluation practices on both improvement and accountability, as depicted in purpose/reporting/remedial support, is very low. This research further found that although the overall focus of teaching evaluation practices is very low on both the accountability and improvement, evaluation practices are more oriented towards enhancing quality rather than towards assuring quality, but non-significant difference.

Introduction

The last decades have observed increasing demands from the public and the governments for evaluating the performance of universities at large. This phenomenon has consequently led to the measures for evaluating the performance of faculty members in universities (Harrison et al., 2020; Iglesias Pérez, Vidal-Puga, & Pino-Juste, 2020; Shao, Anderson & Newsome, 2007). For example, many scholars believe that teacher evaluation practices have become widespread to meet demands for improvement and accountability in higher education (Akour&Hammad, 2020; Hourcade, Parette& Anderson, 2003; Nasser & Fresko, 2002; Yang, Talmy, Zhu, Li, Wang, Zhang ... & Zhou, 2017). The performance of university faculty members is generally assumed to be evaluated based on their effectiveness in teaching, research, scholarship, creative work, and the services offered to the community (Akleh&Wahab, 2020; Akour&Hammad, 2020; Hornstein, 2017; Iglesias Pérez et al., 2020). This is an established fact that teaching is an important component of the roles and responsibilities assigned to faculty members of universities and, therefore, faculty members are particularly being held accountable for the quality of their teaching (Hounsell, 2009; Moran, 2017;). For example, Seldin (2004) argued that faculty members are being asked to provide solid evidence of the quality of their classroom teaching. Considering teachers' evaluation process as an effective tool for determining the performance of faculty members, several different measures and parameters have been adopted by both public and private universities for evaluating the

performance of their teachers (Amin & Khan, 2009; Leffter&Puia, 2010; Moran, 2017). These include but are not limited to students' ratings, peer evaluation, self-assessment, classroom observation, evaluation by administrators, and students' achievement and competence testing (Akour&Hammad, 2020; Harrison et al., 2020; Hornstein, 2017; Iglesias Pérez et al., 2020).

In this context, the universities are placing an increasing emphasis on the evaluating teaching of the faculty members. As a result, universities are placing an increasing emphasis on the evaluation of teaching quality of their faculty members. The evaluation of teaching in universities from the perspective of quality has two key dimension. First is the quality assurance and the second is quality enhancement. The quality has been defined in terms of excellence, value for money, fit for the purpose, and transformation (Biggs, 2001; Dicker, Garcia, Kelly, &Mulrooney, 2019; Harvey, 2011). This has led to two approaches to quality i.e., quality assurance and quality enhancement (Biggs, 2001, 2003; Elassy, 2015; Elken, &Stensaker, 2018; Filippakou& Tapper, 2008; Williams, 2016).

Quality assurance in this context refers to accountability by assuring that policies, procedures, and practices are in place to achieve and maintain quality (Biggs, 2003; Elken, &Stensaker, 2018; Williams, 2016). The quality assurance practices, although, may be internal or external but most of the scholars are of the view that quality assurance refers to the all types of external procedures, monitoring, reviews, audits and evaluation for assuring that standards are being met in higher education (Biggs, 2001, Cheng, 2011; Elassy, 2015; Elken, &Stensaker, 2018; Filippakou& Tapper, 2008; Green, 1994; Williams, 2016). Biggs (2003) termed quality assurance as retrospective, bureaucratic, summative, punitive, and is generally based on accountability. The retrospective concept of quality implies that it can be easily measured against the predetermined and external set of standards (Williams, 2016). Likewise, Harvey (2011) asserted that quality assurance procedures are generally focused on assuring the quality of provisions to satisfy the stakeholder.

Quality enhancement in this context refers to the improvement (Biggs, 2003; Cheng, 2011; Williams, 2016). Quality enhancement focuses on two elements in the context of higher education: First, quality enhancement focuses on enhancing and improving learners' knowledge, skills, attributes, abilities, and their potential for learning (Elassy, 2015; Williams, 2016). Second, QE focuses on improving the quality of study programmes and of institutions of study (Filippakou& Tapper, 2008; Williams, 2016). Furthermore, quality enhancement approaches generally place emphasis on transforming and enhancing students' learning experiences (Biggs, 2003; Harvey, 2011; Williams, 2016). Quality enhancement approaches are focused on continuous measures for improving effectiveness of students' learning experiences (Biggs, 2003; Cheng, 2011; Elken&Stensaker, 2018; Williamson, 2016). Biggs (2003) termed quality enhancement as prospective QA, collegial, formative, reward-based, and are generally based on improvement. Quality enhancement approaches place emphasis on processes of teaching and learning, linked more with development and improvement, bottom-up, qualitative, autonomy, and are present- and future-oriented (Biggs, 2003; Cheng, 2011; Harvey, 2011; Iacovidou, Gibbs, &Zopiatis, 2009; Williams, 2016).

The aforementioned approaches to quality (quality assurance and quality enhancement) inform universities to develop their policies and practices in accordance with their philosophies. In line with these two approaches to quality, the policies and practices for evaluation of teaching in universities are either on accountability, or improvement, or on both. The universities mostly maintain balance in accountability and improvement needs while developing their policies and implementing practices for evaluation of teaching (Biggs, 2003; Elassy, 2015; Hansen, Geschwind, Kivistö, Pekkola, Pinheiro, &Pulkkinen, 2019; Williams, 2016). Hounsell (2009) also believes that teaching evaluation is widely seen not only as necessary step towards accountability of teachers, but also as an integral part of good professional practice and systematic development of teaching expertise (Barnes, Fives, &Dacey, 2017; Elassy, 2015; Harvey, 2011; Williams, 2016). Many international universities have, therefore, developed and implemented solid and research-based teaching evaluation practices that are likely to address the needs of accountability and improvement (Barnes et al., 2017; Bastian, Patterson & Pan, 2018; Tatto& Pippin, 2017).

The most commonly used practices for evaluation of teaching in universities include students' evaluation of teaching, self-evaluation, evaluation by peers, evaluation by staff of professional development and evaluation by the head of the department or by the senior faculty (Arreola, 2000; Harrison et al., 2020; Iglesias Pérez et al., 2020; Seldin, 2004). The literature reveals that universities make use of any one or more practices for the evaluation of teaching with variation in the methods and techniques (Bastian et al., 2018; Iglesias Pérez et al., 2020). Furthermore, all these teaching evaluation practices, with varied methods, may be used by universities both for accountability improvement. It is the not the evaluation method, mode, or technique that determines its orientation towards accountability or improvement, but the way teaching evaluation practices are used by the universities. For example, peer-review of teaching in some universities uses such evaluation procedures that promote it as a management tool (Hansen et al., 2019), whereas it may be used as developmental tool in other universities for improvement purposes (Iglesias Pérez, et al., 2020; Salih, 2013).

The purposes of evaluation of teaching in universities may be either improvement-oriented or accountability oriented. For example, the primary purpose of students' evaluation teaching is formative, and is intended for

improving teaching quality teaching. (Hornstein, 2017). But the summative purpose of students' evaluation of teaching is to judge overall performance of faculty for accountability purpose and use its results for tenure, promotion, recognition and reward purposes (Centra, 1993; Galbraith, Merrill, & Kline, 2012; Hamermesh & Parker, 2005). Linse (2017) also argued that many universities use students' evaluation for making personnel decisions and to rewards faculty, in addition to its use for improvement of instructions. Research shows that if evaluation of teaching is intended to use for improvement purposes, then universities are likely to arrange such sessions in which faculty may have an opportunity to work with an expert teacher to improve teaching (Biggs, 2003; Linse, 2017).

The peer review of teaching is also used for evaluation of teaching with dual purposes. Peer evaluation may be used for professional development, seeking formative feedback, reflection and for accountability purposes (Hammersley-Fletcher & Orsmond, 2004; Iglesias Pérez, et al., 2020). Similarly, the use of portfolio as an evaluation tool has also dual purposes. The formative use of portfolio is improvement-led, while summative use of portfolio in universities is generally accountability-oriented (Akleh, & Wahab, 2020; Buckridge, 2008; Seldin, 2004). An important purpose teaching evaluation is to provide feedback to teachers on the quality of their teaching. When used for improvement purposes, timing, details, and modes of feedback play important role (Dawson, Henderson, Mahoney, Phillips, Ryan, Boud & Molloy, 2019). In summary, the methods and techniques of teaching evaluation practices have dual purposes and are used for enhancing quality when they promote self-reflection, professional capabilities, and provide feedback (Zeichner & Wray, 2001). On the other hand, the accountability led approaches to the evaluation of teaching are generally used as a managerial tool and are less effective in improving quality of teaching and students' learning experiences (Biggs, 2003; Hornstein, 2017; Iglesias Pérez, et al., 2020).

The fundamental aim of any teacher evaluation system should not only be the provision of effective services to the students by making teachers accountable but it must also be designed and developed to encourage and guide teachers so that they can perform their teaching responsibilities more effectively and efficiently. In the context of Pakistan, such teaching evaluation system is needed for universities that is likely to address notion of accountability and improvement. The existing teacher evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan are traditional, obsolete, inconclusive, and generally rely on single data source by engaging untrained evaluators (Anjum, Yasmeen, & Khan, 2011; Aslam, 2011; Rasheed et al., 2011). Such traditional evaluation practices fail to measure adequately multidimensional nature and comprehensive scope of teachers' position and, thus, do not have a clear focus either on enhancing the quality of teaching or addressing accountability needs. It is, therefore, very important to address this important theme and to investigate the nature of teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan.

In above-mentioned context, the policies and practices for evaluation of teaching in universities are guided by the philosophy of either quality assurance (accountability), quality enhancement (improvement), or by the both. Furthermore, orientation of teaching evaluation practices towards quality assurance and enhancement is likely to influence the outcomes of processes and practices. Moreover, balanced approach towards evaluation of teaching practices may serve the purpose of improvement and accountability in the context of universities of Pakistan. However, research working is lacking in the context of analysis of teaching evaluation practices from the perspective of their orientation towards quality assurance or quality enhancement in universities of Pakistan. This research, therefore, investigates the nature of teaching evaluation practices in the universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance, quality enhancement or the both.

Research Objectives

This research investigates the nature of teaching evaluation practices in the universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability), quality enhancement (i.e., improvement), or the both. The key objectives of this research were as follows:

- To explore the nature of teaching evaluation processes in the universities of Pakistan, as reflected in policies, from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement (i.e., improvement).
- To examine the nature of teaching evaluation practices in the universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement (i.e., improvement).
- To examine the extent to which teaching evaluation policies and practices in the universities of Pakistan have mixed orientation towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) and quality enhancement (i.e., improvement).
- To examine the difference, if any, between the accountability-led and improvement-led orientation of teaching evaluation practices in the universities of Pakistan.

Method

Research Design

This research used triangulation mixed-method research design. Creswell, Plano Clark, Gutmann and Hanson (2003) asserted that triangulation mixed method is the most common approach to mixing different methods. This design is used to get different (quantitative and qualitative) but complementary set of data on the same topic to understand the problem (Creswell, 2011). Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected and analyzed simultaneously to gain the depth in the results (Ponce & Pagán-Maldonado, 2015). In this research design, both qualitative and quantitative data are collected and analyzed separately but findings are integrated in interpretation section (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2007). Data were collected and analyzed in two concurrent phases.

Phase I

In phase I, the policy and practice documents related to evaluation of teaching were collected from the HEC and from the universities in Pakistan. A total of 71 policy and practice documents related to the evaluation of teaching were found from 130 higher education institutions of Pakistan, using different sources. These policy documents were either publicly available at the websites of the HEC and universities or were collected from the administration and management of respective universities. For the analysis of data, both thematic analysis and content analysis techniques were used. In alignment with objective of research, the focus of documents in data collection and analysis was on investigating the nature of teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement.

Phase II

In phase II, the survey technique was used to identify the nature of current teacher evaluation practices in the universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation towards improvement and accountability. For this, questionnaire and semi-structured interview were used. This questionnaire was based on extensive review of literature related to the key purposes of evaluation of teaching practices from the perspective of accountability and improvement. Questionnaire contained 26 statements related to purposes and reporting of the teaching evaluation results, other than demographic variables. Of these 26 statements, nine were focused on improvement-led statements and six were accountability-led statements. Five statements were related to the reporting of the teaching evaluation results for different purposes. Two statements were related to provision of remedial support to students and same number of statements were about potential orientation of teaching evaluation practices. Two were related to accountability and improvement orientation of the overall teaching evaluation practices. All statements were either designed on five-point scale or on a "Yes/No". The reliability of the tool was noted as .89.

The faculty members and administrative from 130 higher education institutions (HEIs) of Pakistan served as population of the study. From this population, a sample of 887 faculty members and administrative staff of the QEC were randomly selected using cluster and stratified sampling techniques. The tool was distributed to 887 respondents, and 617 responded back. The response rate of questionnaire was observed as 69.56. Semi-structured interview were also conducted from 27 faculty. For data analysis, frequencies, percentages, mean, SD, t-test, chi-square, and independent sample t-tests were used. Results are given in the following section.

Results and Discussion

This results of research have been presented in two sections in relation to research objectives. First, results have been presented in relation to the nature of teaching evaluation processes in the universities of Pakistan, as reflected in policies of the HEC and of universities, from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement (i.e., improvement). Second, results have been presented in relation to the nature of teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan from the perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement (i.e., improvement), or a mixed orientation towards both quality assurance (i.e., accountability) and quality enhancement (i.e., improvement).

Orientation of Teaching Evaluation Practices as Reflected in Policies

In this section, the key results of research have been presented in relation to the nature of teaching evaluation processes in universities of Pakistan, as reflected in policies of HEC and of universities, from perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement (i.e., improvement). The analysis of data was based on 71 policy and practice documents related to the evaluation of teaching from 130 higher education institutions of Pakistan. For the analysis of data, thematic analysis and latent content analysis (a form of content analysis) were used. Table 1 presents the summary of key findings, emerged from the analysis of policies about teaching evaluation practices for their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or quality enhancement (i.e., improvement).

Table 1. Orientation of teaching evaluation practices, as reflected in policies

Key Themes	Orientation of teaching evaluation practices, as reflected in policies
Design of teaching evaluation practices, emerged from various forms of evaluation (Students' evaluation; Peer evaluation; Supervisor evaluation by the HOD/ Dean; Portfolios)	Improvement-oriented policies (QE)
	Criteria set by department in consultation with QEC.
	Focus on amending policies to meet specific requirements of discipline.
	Implementation of teaching evaluation practices by departments.
Purposes of evaluation of teaching	Plans of teaching evaluation by the department.
	Accountability-oriented policies (QA)
	Policies and criteria in accordance with guidelines of QAA of the HEC.
	Top-down approach – QEC consults top administration of university.
Reporting of the results of evaluation	Evaluation team comprising senior faculty members and QEC.
	Improvement-oriented purposes (QE)
	Formative purposes.
	Focus on identification of strengths and areas for improvement.
Reporting of the results of evaluation	To collect students' feedback for improvement purposes.
	Accountability-oriented purposes (QA)
	Summative purposes
	For recognition/reward purposes.
Reporting of the results of evaluation	To identify students' satisfaction about teaching method and courses.
	Improvement-oriented reporting (QE)
	Rare sharing of evaluation results with concerned teacher/HOD/Dean.
	QEC provide support to departments in addressing the areas for improvement, training, capacity building, and workshops.
Reporting of the results of evaluation	Accountability-oriented reporting (QA)
	Sharing of results by QEC with Vice-Chancellor, for accountability.

The first theme emerged from analysis of policies was to explore the design and implementation of teaching evaluation practices for their orientation towards improvement and accountability. Table 1 clearly shows that universities put focus on designing both improvement-led and accountability-oriented policies. The focus on improvement-oriented policies is clear as the criteria for the evaluation of teaching is set at department level in consultation with QEC. Likewise, policies are subject to minor amendment to meet specific requirements of the discipline. Furthermore, planning and implementation of teaching evaluation practices is mostly done by the departments. The focus on accountability-oriented policies is clear as the policies and criteria for the evaluation of teaching is developed in accordance with guidelines of the Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) of the HEC. It was also emerged from findings that universities generally follow top-down approach for the evaluation of teaching in consultation with top management of the university, and evaluation teams comprise senior faculty members and staff of the QEC.

The second theme emerged from the analysis of policies was to explore the purposes of teaching evaluation practices for their orientation towards improvement and accountability. Table 1 shows that universities put a focus on formulating both improvement- and accountability-oriented purposes of evaluation practices. The improvement-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation are evident as policies state that teaching evaluation practices are used for formative purposes, put focus on identification of strengths and areas for improvement, and collect students' feedback for improvement purposes. The accountability-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation are evident as policies state that teaching evaluation practices are used for summative purposes, for recognition/reward purposes, and for identifying students' satisfaction about methods of teaching.

The third theme emerged from the analysis of policies was to explore how the results of teaching evaluation practices are reported for their orientation either towards improvement and accountability. Table 1 shows that universities put a very low focus on reporting of evaluation results to the stakeholder, both improvement- and accountability-oriented purposes. The undermine focus on improvement-oriented reporting of results of the evaluation is evident as evaluation results are rarely shared with concerned teacher/HOD/Dean. However, the QEC provide support to the departments in addressing the areas for improvement, training, capacity building, and workshops. The focus on accountability-oriented reporting of evaluation results is evident as QEC shares the results with the Vice-Chancellor for accountability purposes.

The analysis of policy documents revealed that teaching evaluation practices are not satisfying the purposes of accountability and improvement in universities of Pakistani, but these processes are conducted to collect data for fulfilling administrative requirements by the HEC. The analysis of policy documents further revealed that few teaching evaluation practices collect feedback about the teaching effectiveness of faculty, but limited evidence exists about effective use of this feedback for improvement purpose or for engaging stakeholders in assuring or enhancing the quality of teaching.

Orientation of Teaching Evaluation Practices from the Perspective of QA and QE

This section presents results in relation to nature of teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan from perspective of their orientation either towards quality assurance (i.e., accountability) or towards quality enhancement (i.e., improvement), or mixed orientation towards both quality assurance and enhancement. The results of the analysis are further focused on three factors related teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan i.e., the purposes of teaching evaluation practices, the reporting of evaluation results, provision of remedial support to the faculty, and overall orientation of teaching evaluation practices either towards quality assurance or towards quality enhancement, or a mixed orientation towards both quality assurance and quality enhancement. Table 2 presents the results related to improvement-oriented (quality enhancement) purposes of teaching evaluation practices perceived by university teachers in Pakistan. For this, frequencies with “yes” and percentages were calculated.

Table 2: Improvement-oriented (quality enhancement) purposes of teaching evaluation practices

Improvement-oriented purposes of teachers' evaluation (n=617)	f “Yes”	%age
Feedback on learning experiences of students.	271	43.92
To improve students' learning experiences.	234	37.93
To identify professional development needs of teachers.	157	25.45
To provide diagnostic feedback to faculty about their teaching.	283	45.87
To inform teachers about the strengths and areas for improvement.	097	15.72
To inform teachers for improving their teaching practices.	087	14.10
Teachers reflect upon their practices and set improvement goals.	051	08.27
To disseminate good practices.	024	03.89
To strengthen teaching as a profession.	191	30.96
Overall	155	25.12

Table 2 indicates that university teachers believe that improvement-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation practices are mostly lacking in universities of Pakistan. Less than half of the sample faculty members believe that provision of diagnostic feedback to the faculty about their teaching is the purpose of teaching evaluation practices. Likewise, less than half of the sample faculty believe that provision of feedback to students on their learning experiences is the purpose of teaching evaluation practices. Table also shows that around one-third of sample faculty members believe improvement of students' learning experiences, strengthening teaching as a profession, and identification of teachers' professional development needs are determined as the purpose of teaching evaluation practices. It is also evident from Table 2 that only less than 10% faculty members believe that informing teachers about their strengths and areas for improvement, helping teachers for improvement, reflection on practices, and dissemination of good practices as purposes of teaching evaluation practices. It is further evident from Table 2 that only one-fourth (25%) of the sample faculty members believe that purposes of teaching evaluation practices oriented on the philosophy of quality enhancement or improvement. It is also concluded that focus of teaching evaluation practices on improvement, as depicted in purposes, is very low. Table 3 presents results related to accountability-oriented (quality assurance) purposes of teaching evaluation practices perceived by university teachers in Pakistan. For this, frequencies with “yes” and percentages were calculated.

Table 3: Accountability-oriented (quality assurance) purposes of teaching evaluation practices

Accountability-led purposes of teachers' evaluation	f “Yes”	%age
Critical evaluation of teaching methods/strategies.	194	31.44
For raising teaching/learning standards.	259	41.98
For purpose of teachers' accountability.	103	16.69
Because it is required by my university for administrative purposes.	162	26.26
For recognition/reward purposes (<i>probation/tenure/promotion/salary/awards</i>).	059	09.56
Reporting of data on quality to the HEC and other internal/external bodies.	110	17.83
Overall	148	23.99

Table 3 indicates that university teachers believe that accountability-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation practices are mostly lacking in universities of Pakistan. Less than half of the sample faculty members believe that that purpose of teaching evaluation practices is to raise teaching/learning standards. Likewise, around 30% of the sample faculty members believe that provision of diagnostic feedback to faculty on their teaching and critical evaluation of teaching methods/strategies are the purposes of teaching evaluation practices. Table 3 also shows that only less than one-fifth of the sample faculty members believe that teaching evaluations are required by university for administrative purposes, or is used for reporting of data on quality to the HEC and other

internal/external bodies, or the purpose of teachers' accountability, or for recognition/reward purposes (i.e., probation/tenure/promotion/salary/awards). It is further evident from the Table 3 that only less than one-fourth (23.99%) of sample faculty members believe that purposes of teaching evaluation practices oriented on philosophy of quality assurance or accountability. It is further concluded that focus of teaching evaluation practices on accountability, as depicted in purposes, is very low. Graphical representation of accountability-oriented and improvement-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation practices in the universities of Pakistan is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Accountability-oriented (quality assurance) purposes of teaching evaluation practices

It is evident from Figure 1 that improvement-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation practices have slightly higher values than accountability-oriented purposes. The same has also been depicted in Table 2 and Table 3, which indicate that 25.12% of sample faculty members believe that purposes of teaching evaluation practices are oriented on philosophy of quality assurance or accountability, slightly higher than 23.99% of the sample faculty who believe that purposes of teaching evaluation practices are oriented on the philosophy of quality enhancement or improvement. It is clearly evident from Table 2, Table 3, and Figure 1 that although focus of teaching evaluation practices both on accountability and improvement, as depicted in purposes, is very low, the later (QE) has slightly higher values than the former (QA). To examine whether this difference in focus on accountability-oriented purposes and improvement-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation practices is significant, Chi-Square test was applied and results are shown in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4. Orientation of teaching evaluation practices (Improvement-/Accountability-oriented)

Orientation of Teachers' Evaluation (n=617)	No	Yes	Total
Improvement-led	462	155	617
Accountability-led	469	148	617
Overall	931	303	1234

Table 5. Chi-Square Tests on orientation of teaching evaluation by purpose (n=617)

Chi-Square Tests	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.214 ^a	1	.643
Continuity Correction ^b	.157	1	.691
Likelihood Ratio	.214	1	.643
N of Valid Cases	1234		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 151.50.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

The table 5 shows that the value of Chi-Square (χ^2) is statistically non-significant: $\chi^2(1)=.214, p>.0005$. It can be, therefore, concluded that statistically non-significant difference exists in teaching evaluation practices for their orientation towards accountability or improvement. It is concluded that although the focus of teaching evaluation practices both on accountability and improvement, as depicted in purposes, is although very low but it is significantly equal. It is also inferred that there is non-significant association between improvement-

orientated and accountability-oriented purposes of teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan. Table 6 presents results related to improvement- and accountability-oriented reporting of teaching evaluation practices perceived by university teachers in Pakistan. For this, frequencies with “yes” and percentages were calculated.

Table 6. Accountability- and improvement-oriented reporting of teaching evaluation results

Orientation of reporting of evaluation results	f “Yes”	%age
Teacher concerned (Improvement-led)	082	13.29
Staff of QEC (Improvement-led)	291	47.16
Chair of the department (Improvement- and accountability-led)	138	22.37
Dean (Accountability-led)	068	11.02
Promotion/review committee (Accountability-/reward-led)	022	03.57
Overall	120	19.45

Table 6 indicates that less than half of the sample faculty members believe that results of teaching evaluation are reported to the staff of QEC for improvement purposes and only 13.29% faculty believes that concerned teachers are informed about the results of evaluation for improving their teaching. This shows a low focus of teaching evaluation practices on the reporting of results for improvement purposes. Likewise, table 5 further shows that 11.02% of the sample faculty members believe that results of teaching evaluation are reported to the Dean for improvement purposes and only 3.57% faculty believes that results of evaluation are used for recognition, reward, and promotion purposes. This shows a very low focus of teaching evaluation practices on the reporting of results for accountability purposes. It is clearly evident from Table 5 that although focus of teaching evaluation practices both on accountability and improvement, as depicted in reporting of results, is very low, the later (QE) has slightly higher values than former (QA). To examine whether this difference in focus on accountability-oriented reporting and improvement-oriented reporting of the evaluation results is significant, Chi-Square test was applied and results are shown in Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7: Orientation of teaching evaluation from reporting perspective (n=617)

Orientation of Teachers’ Evaluation	No	Yes	Total
Improvement-led reporting	447	170	617
Accountability-led reporting	541	076	617
Overall	988	246	1234

Table 8. Chi-Square Tests on orientation of teaching evaluation from reporting perspective

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1234.000 ^a	3	.000
Likelihood Ratio	1710.687	3	.000
N of Valid Cases	1234		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 74.00

The table 8 shows that the value of Chi-Square (χ^2) is statistically significant: $\chi^2(3)=1234.00$, $p<.0005$. It can be, therefore, concluded that statistically significant difference exists in teaching evaluation practices for their orientation towards accountability or improvement. It is inferred that there is significant association between improvement-orientated and accountability-oriented reporting of teaching evaluation results in universities of Pakistan. Table 9 presents results related to improvement- and accountability-oriented remedial support that is provided to teachers in teaching evaluation practices as perceived by university teachers in Pakistan. For this, mean and SD were calculated.

Table 9. Orientation of teaching evaluation about provision of remedial support

Provision of remedial support (N= 617)	Mean	SD
Mentoring sessions by supervisor (HoD/Dean/Director etc.) to help teacher.	2.96	1.01
Provision of professional development to teachers by university/QEC.	2.97	1.00

Table 9 shows that the mean values of the both aspects about the provision of remedial support to teachers in teaching evaluation practices is less than 3. It can be concluded that faculty members believe that remedial support to teachers in forms of mentoring sessions or professional development is not provided to teachers. It is, thus, clear that orientation of teaching evaluation practices either towards accountability or improvement is lacking in the provision of remedial support to teachers. Table 10 presents results about overall perceived orientation of the teacher evaluation practices either towards quality assurance or enhancement.

Table 10. Overall perceived orientation of the teacher evaluation practices

Overall perceived orientation of teachers' evaluation	Mean	SD	df	Sig
Orientation towards enhancing quality (improvement).	3.21	0.95	1232	.85
Orientation towards assuring quality (accountability).	3.20	0.89		
Overall impact of teachers' evaluation	3.21	0.92		

Table 10 indicates that mean values for overall orientation of teacher evaluation practices towards enhancing quality is slightly greater than towards assuring quality as perceived by university teachers. This difference is, however, non-significant ($p > .005$) and, therefore, there is no difference in focus on both improvement or on accountability in overall teaching evaluation practices in universities of Pakistan. It is further clear that the focus on both accountability and improvement is very low (with mean of 3.21).

Conclusion

A very useful set of conclusions were drawn from this research. First, it was concluded that universities put focus on designing both improvement-led and accountability-oriented policies. Second, it was concluded that universities put focus on formulating both improvement- and accountability-oriented purposes of evaluation practices. Third, it was concluded that universities put a very low focus on reporting of evaluation results to the stakeholder, both improvement- and accountability-oriented purposes. Fourth, policy documents revealed that evaluation practices are not satisfying the purposes of accountability and improvement in universities of Pakistan. Fifth, analysis of policy documents further revealed that few teaching evaluation practices collect feedback about the teaching effectiveness of faculty, but limited evidence exists about effective use of this feedback for improvement purposes or for engaging stakeholders in assuring/enhancing quality of teaching.

Sixth conclusion was that the focus of teaching evaluation practices on both improvement and accountability, as depicted in purposes, is very low. Seventh, although the focus of the teaching evaluation practices both on accountability and improvement, as depicted in purposes, is very low, the later has slightly higher values than the former but this difference is not significant. Eighth, it was concluded that although the focus of evaluation practices both on accountability and improvement, as depicted in reporting of results, is very low, the later has slightly higher values than former but not significant. Ninth, it was concluded that remedial support to teachers in forms of mentoring sessions or professional development is not provided to teachers, both from the perspective of accountability or improvement. Finally, although the overall focus of teaching evaluation practices on both accountability and improvement is very low, evaluation practices are more oriented towards enhancing quality than towards assuring quality. This difference is, however, non-significant.

Recommendations

The analysis of policy documents in this research clearly revealed that evaluation practices are not satisfying the purposes of accountability and improvement in universities of Pakistan. Likewise, results of quantitative data analysis revealed that focus of teaching evaluation practices on both improvement and accountability, as depicted in purposes/reporting/remedial support, is very low. Overall focus of teaching evaluation practices on both accountability and improvement was also observed to be very low. On the bases of these results, it is recommended for policymakers to deice such policies that address the needs of both quality assurance and of quality enhancement or improvement. Likewise, it is also recommended that academics need to work on the appropriate implementation of teaching evaluation practices in consistent with the spirt of the processes. All the components of teaching evaluation practices must be dealt with care and holistic approach be adopted for implementation of evaluation practices. It is also recommended that loop of the teaching evaluation practices must be closed to achieve the outcomes of the processes.

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